

Bias in Numbers Part 2: The Mathematics of Superposition

It has been said that any number divided by 0 essentially “breaks” arithmetic and returns an indeterminate value. However, what does it actually mean for a number to be indeterminate? Isn't a number just a measure of quantity? How can there ever be an indeterminate quantity? Furthermore, if 0 is a real number on the number line then shouldn't it be treated the same as any other number in terms of it being “divisor-able”?

The reason that division by zero is not allowed in contemporary mathematics is because it leads to paradoxes. For example, suppose that division by zero was allowed. Then if one were to take the equation $X \cdot 0 = 0$ and solve for X, X would always need to be equal to $0/0$ no matter its value.

See the example below:

$$X \cdot 0 = 0$$

(Since any number multiplied by zero is equal to zero because zero instantiations of any quantity would always return something with “0 quantity”)

Substituting any number for x such as 1,2,3 or n would establish the following:

$$1 \cdot 0 = 0$$

$$2 \cdot 0 = 0$$

$$3 \cdot 0 = 0$$

$$N \cdot 0 = 0$$

Now if any of these numbers multiplied by 0 equals 0, then one should also be able to divide by 0 on both sides of the equation to get the number in question alone.

So:

$$1 \cdot 0 = 0$$

$$1 = 0/0$$

$$2 \cdot 0 = 0$$

$$2 = 0/0$$

The Paradox

Now according to this logic, if $0/0 = 2$ and $0/0 = 1$, then shouldn't 2 also be equal to 1? This of course introduces a paradox. How can 2 and 1 both be equal to $0/0$ yet at the same time not be equal to each other? It is this that paradox that essentially “breaks” arithmetic.

While on the surface this may seem to be enough to simply state that “division by 0 should not be allowed”, perhaps this actually unveils a much deeper phenomenon. For if every possible

number is equal to $0/0$ yet $0/0$ does not necessarily equal every possible number, what does this tell you about the ontology of $0/0$? What causes it to have these qualities?

$0/0$ as a Super-Number and Quantum Superposition

For a little bit of background, twentieth century quantum physics introduced the idea of “superposition” which established that prior to measurement or interaction, all particles essentially exist in all possible eigenstates at once. Rather than existing as definitive particles with definitive properties, in their pre-measurement states they exist only as probabilistic wave functions that evolve in accordance to the Schrodinger Equation. However, even though the probabilities of their potential properties could be calculated via the Schrodinger Equation, the properties that they will eventually take on are unknown. Once they are measured however, these potential eigenstates collapse into one definitive state and it is at this point when the particle takes on “real” measurable definitive properties. Before it was measured, it can be said that its wave function could end up collapsing in any possible way. However, after measurement the wave function no longer can and the particle must take on only discrete definitive properties. Now, it was originally the idea of Brazilian logician Walter Gomide to relate this concept to the peculiar properties of $0/0$.

Defining $0/0$ as a Concept Number

For if this logic is applied to $0/0$, then it could be said that $0/0$ is essentially a “super-number” and a concept number like 1, 0 or ∞ . While 1 would indicate “something”, 0 “nothing” and ∞ “everything”, $0/0$ would similarly indicate “super-thing”. Furthermore, just as 0, 1 and ∞ have special properties ($\infty + x$ is always ∞ , $0 * x$ is always 0, x^0 is always 1), so too $0/0$ would have a special property that x always = $0/0$ and that once $0/0$ is assigned to a number, it could no longer be assigned to any other number in that context.

For it can be said that $0/0$ could be set equal to any value. This equality can then be proved by multiplying said value by 0 and then dividing by 0. However, once $0/0$ is set equal to a value, it collapses and no longer exists as $0/0$ but only as that value it collapsed into.

For example, in the case of $1*0 = 0$ and $2*0 = 0$, it can be said that once the numbers 1 or 2 are isolated and set equal to $0/0$, that those subsequent $0/0$'s have collapsed into the contexts of 1 or 2 and can therefore no longer be applied to any other number. For even though $0/0$ would technically equal 1 in one context and 2 in another context, it can never actually be equal to both in the same context. This is because $0/0$ can never ‘transfer’ contexts since once it is established in a context it automatically collapses since it’s being defined as something thus collapsing its superposition of states.

See below:

Context A:

$$2*0 = 0$$

$$2 = 0/0$$

(At this point the superposition of 0/0 has already been defined as 2 since it has already been established in the context. Therefore, it is no longer a superposition but now 2. This superposition therefore no longer exists outside of the context of the 2 and therefore can not be set equal to any other number in any other context)

Context B:

$$1 * 0 = 0$$

$$1 = 0/0$$

(At this point the superposition of 0/0 has already been defined as 1 since it has already been established in the context. Therefore, it is no longer a superposition but now 1. This superposition therefore no longer exists outside of the context of the 1 and therefore can not be set equal to any other number in any other context)

0/0 Always Collapses When Interacting With a Context!

Therefore, once 0/0 is established as either equal to 1 or 2 it could no longer be applied anywhere else. For at this point its superposition of being all numbers at once has collapsed into only one number. This one number is then treated like any other definitive number and could not simply be set equal to any other number since it is now definitive and no longer 0/0. It should be noted that the second 0/0 is set equal to anything it is then defined within a context and thus collapses into the number on the other side of the equal sign. Therefore, it cannot be subsequently transferred into any other context and used as an equalizer (since once 0/0 has entered a context and been set to a number such as 1, it is no longer 0/0 but only 1 and 1 cannot equal to 2).

Quantum Entanglements

This quality of 0/0 being unable to survive “shifts” in context also relates to quantum superposition. For the concept of a superposition’s “collapse” upon contact relates closely to the mechanism in which a quantum wave function collapses. While somewhat controversial, it is in my opinion that the reason the quantum wave function collapses when measured into a definitive eigenstate is due to its superposition being established within a context. To elaborate, prior to being measured by an observer, the quantum particle exists only within a wave function that can eventually exist in accordance with potential probabilities via the Schrodinger Equation. However, once the quantum particle is measured or observed, it interacts with the “observer” thus forcing it to enter the context of the observer. Once it enters the “context” of an observer it can no longer exist as a superposition and must take on definitive properties to fit into the “reality” of the observers context. This happens because when it is without context it is essentially simply part of the “infinite whole” without separations. Once a context measures it however, it has a light shone upon it. This light is shone upon on a segment of the infinite whole (entitled the wave function) and therefore the wave function’s superposition is forced to collapse into a definitive state since it has become part of the context of the observer. Before being measured the wave function could exist in any potential manner since its true nature was unrevealed as it was shrouded in all-encompassing darkness. However, when the observer measures it, “light” is shone on the darkness that is the superposition forcing the superposition to

reveal its true definitive state to the observer. This phenomenon is also known as ‘quantum entanglement’ since the context of the particle becomes ‘entangled’ with the context of the observer.

Equals Signs Are Mathematical Entanglements

Relating this to 0/0; Introducing equals signs are essentially paramount to creating entanglements. For equals signs force 2 contexts (one on the left side of the equals sign and one on the right side of the equals sign) to interact with one another and therefore fit their realities in accordance with one another. It is this phenomenon of “setting arithmetic terms equal to other arithmetic terms” that essentially entangles these two contexts, each on opposite ends of the equals sign. This can be likened to measurement. Once one side of the equation figures out how to fit its reality into the other side of the equation then the two are considered part of the same equation and therefore part of the same context. It is at this point that they become entangled.

For example, take a trivial algebraic equation of $3x = 6$:

Context A:

$3x$

Context B:

6

Entanglement - Context A+B:

$3x = 6$

At this point the two contexts have learned to fit the other context into their own reality which is what has allowed them to merge contexts

Context A+B

$x = 2$

How Contexts Fit Into One Another’s Reality

This process of $3x$ becoming entangled with 6 essentially begins at the context of the right hand side of the equation, since it is the right hand side of the equation that wants to know more information about the left hand side (the x is on the left side). Once it is established that $x = 2$, both sides of the equation have figured out how to mesh each others realities in a manner that makes sense - IE - $3*2$ on one side has the same number of components as 6 on the other side allowing them to relate to each other and coexist in one combined context. For finding similarities in each others contexts is essentially the property of entanglement that allows two contexts to “fit” into the same reality and merge into one “whole” context. However, it should be noted that the second the $3x$ is set equal to the 6 the two sides of the equation are already entangled. For even if there is an element of “hidden-ness” to one context from the viewpoint of the other, once they have began the observation process they have already become entangled, since their collapse from their wave functions have taken place (for even though x is hidden in

$3x = 6$, since it is known that the two are equal to one another it can be eventually surmised that $x = 2$ from the point in which the two are set equal to one another). Therefore, it can be said that the point at which the equals sign is introduced between $3x$ and 6 is the point at which the two contexts become entangled.

The superposition in this example is never introduced since once $3x$ and 6 are set equal to one another they are essentially in the same context already, entangled and therefore without superposition relative to one another.

Back to 0/0

However, it is implicit that prior to entanglement and the introduction of an equals sign, any context that exists can only relate to other unentangled contexts by viewing them as a superposition. IE - The number 6 when interacting with another context prior to an equals sign can only interact with other contexts in the form $6 * 0 = 0$ and thus $6 = 0/0$. However, once an equals sign is established between the 6 and another number, the two are entangled and therefore can no longer be defined as $0/0$ relative to one another.

Using this logic, 1 cannot be equal to 2 , since once the superposition collapses in $1 = 0/0$ at the point the equals sign is introduced. The $0/0$ has revealed its true identity by establishing the context of 1 (the superposition of $0/0$ has been observed and collapsed into a value of 1 due to the equals sign between them). Therefore, the $0/0$ that collapsed into 1 can no longer be used in any other context since it no longer exists. It has become entangled with the 1 and revealed its true state as the 1 and now cannot exist as any other number. Therefore, if it were tried to set that $0/0$ equal to the 2 , it would not work since that $0/0$ does not exist. Instead only the 1 can be tried and set equal to the 2 which it cannot since 1 does not equal 2 once the two numbers are instantiated in their own contexts.

One question that could emerge from this is why routinely numbers can be set equal to one another even after the equals sign has been dissolved. For example, in the case of $3x = 6$, it can also be established that $3x = 6 = 9-3$. This can be explained since the $3x = 6$ are already combined into one context at the point the equals sign is introduced. Therefore, setting them equal to $9-3$ in another context simply adds an entanglement the second the equals sign between the 6 and the $9-3$ is introduced. Therefore, $3x = 6 = 9-3$ is essentially just one context consisting of two entanglements. Once the equals signs are inserted, the three are already entangled and free to mesh each other's realities in accordance with each other.

0/0 is Different Due to Its Ability to Collapse a Context Altogether

However, for $0/0$, since $0/0$ does not exist in its own context but only as a superposition of states relative from a *different* context, it cannot be combined with equals signs the same way. For $1 = 0/0 = 2$ cannot exist all within the same context, since the superposition of $0/0$ collapses the second it interacts for the first time with the 1 . Therefore, by the time the 2 is introduced there is only a 1 on the other side of the equals sign and no longer a $0/0$. For like entanglement, the second a superposition interacts with a context, the superposition collapses into the reality of the context.

Therefore, it can be seen that $0/0$ essentially indicates a superposition of numbers until it finds a home in an existing context. Once a context interacts with $0/0$, the $0/0$ is forced to reveal its true identity and take on just one definitive state.

However the question remains why multiplying a number by 0 could allow this superposition to be revealed

In the example of $1*0 = 0$ and then $1 = 0/0$, the 1 is being instantiated 0 times, thus effectively eliminating its own state as 1 within its context. The newfound lack of “quantity” in its context is therefore now represented by a mere 0 on the left hand side of the equals sign. Dividing both sides by 0 then re-establishes the 1 on the left hand side of the equation, though on the right hand side divides a lack of quantity by a lack of components (since anything divided by 0 indicates a return to where there is a lack of components). This lack of quantity within a lack of components essentially represents a return to objective superposition that is outside of any context. Therefore, the 1 on the left hand side of the equation has its true primordial state as a superposition exposed when set to $0/0$. However, $0/0$ cannot be maintained within a context and instantaneously collapses into 1 the moment it is introduced into the equation (this moment would be when the 1 is multiplied by 0 since at that moment, $0/0$ could eventually be surmised as 1). Therefore, the $0/0$ though on the right hand side of the equation cannot coexist in the context of the 1 and instead *becomes* the 1 thus eliminating it from the equation instantaneously. It can thus be said that by the time $1 = 0/0$ is introduced, the $0/0$ has already collapsed into the one and does not actually exist in the equation. Therefore, since $0/0$ is now 1 and is not within a proper context, it cannot be transferred to any other context and therefore can never be used to prove it is equal to anything other than what it has collapsed into.

What does this all mean?

Establishing $0/0$ as the number for superposition essentially removes the problem of division by zero causing arithmetic paradoxes. For division by zero is a real operation - it is the return of the quantity in a context back into the context-less infinite which for all numbers > 1 results in a the true objective infinity.

As for $0/0$, it is clear from quantum mechanics that superposition is as much a real phenomenon as is “everything”, “nothing” and “something”. Therefore it too deserves to be represented arithmetically and indeed it does as $0/0$. $0/0$ in this way can be seen as the primordial root from which all numbers arise. Since becoming entangled with another context is what allows “numbers” to form within them and operations to take place, it can be said that $0/0$ collapses into numbers when the $0/0$ is introduced into an equation. It is this equals sign on one side of $0/0$ that establishes the formation of a numerical operation.

The Process of Superposition and Entanglement

This can be likened to how in quantum mechanics a subatomic particles superposition collapses when it becomes entangled with another context. Sure, the subatomic particle can be said to have always existed as a potentiality in the objective superposition. However, from the standpoint of the individual context from which we are measuring from, the subatomic particle

was not entangled with us and therefore only existed as a superposition. Once we tried to observe the subatomic particle and related our context to its context, the two contexts became entangled and us along with the particle then became enjoined with a combined context. Therefore, to us, the subatomic particle has become something real since we can interact with it in our context. It therefore exhibits definitive properties. This process of “entanglement” is the same for numbers. From the standpoint of numbers in their own context, every number outside of it only exists as a superposition of numbers since it is not interacting with them. However once an equals sign becomes introduces to numbers in another context, the 2 contexts relate to each other and therefore become a part of a larger combined context that consists of both numbers on both sides of the equals sign. (Multiplying a number by 0 and then dividing by 0 essentially is just a proof to establish the true ontological identity of said number on the left hand side of the equation as having existed as a superposition relative to any other context).

Note that in this way, the concept of entanglement is also represented in arithmetic. However, unlike 1,0, infinity and 0/0 it does not exist as a quantity but rather as an equals sign. It is what allows two contexts on both sides of an equation to relate to one another and then coexist within a larger context.

What does this mean for the universe?

Arithmetic alone can be used to explain ones place within the universe in this way. One observer from a single perspective (and therefore a single context) can continuously interact with more and more things in the physical universe. This not only broadens his or her subjective perspective, but also expands the “equation” that represents the context as this equation is constantly relating to more and more things in the physical universe and becoming entangled with them. This constant addition of equal signs to the equation of ones context can be used as an explanation for the increase in entropy. Since ones equation of context is always growing and expanding, its information is as well, thus causing its potential configurations and entropy to increase.

Below is a final schematic of the process of arithmetic entanglement:

Everything began as a superposition of 0/0 from the perspective of another context

0/0

Once a context is established, it then has a certain amount of quantities within it (let's say 0)

0

Once this zero interacts with another context (say the context of 3) the two become entangled into a joined context (entanglement is shown by the = sign)

0 -> becomes entangled with 3

The relation between the 0 and the 3 is established

$$0 + x = 3$$

Now the equation becomes entangled with a 6 in another context

$$0 + x + x = 3 + x = 6$$

$$0 + 2x = 3 + x = 6$$

Each step of the way the information needed to resolve this equation increases which is why entropy (or the amount of configurations of possible information for the context) also increases.

Future Articles

Perhaps future articles could shed more light on this process of entanglement and formalize how entropy increasing can relate to the forward flow of time from the perspective of an observer.